

Viscosity of xanthan based drilling fluids : effects of temperature, additives, rheometer geometry

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Xanthan based drilling fluids are characterized for their viscosities using Bohlin and Fann viscometers. These characterizations are performed to study the effect of viscometer geometry, fluid temperature and drilling fluid additives on the measured viscosities. The effect of the measuring geometry is observed to be insignificant for the drilling fluid containing xanthan polymer only. The viscosities of the fluids are observed to decrease with an increase in temperature. For the drilling fluids containing additives, the viscosity curves obtained at various temperatures are reduced to master curves using parameters defined using the molecular theories of polymers. The master curves can be used to obtain viscosity values within and beyond the shear rates, temperatures and the polymer concentrations used to generate these curves.

Drilling fluid constitutes an important aspect of drilling operations¹. Its importance requires that it be pre-evaluated in a laboratory for successful drilling. It is most commonly evaluated for its viscosity, which is used to calculate friction pressure losses through drill pipe and pipe-bore wall annulus and evaluate its cuttings-carrying capacity, and to determine drill bit penetration rate². A higher fluid viscosity is required for better drilled-cuttings transport, but a lower viscosity is desired for lower pressure losses through drill-pipe and faster drill-bit penetration rates. The diverse range of viscosity values needs that the drilling fluid viscosity be closely monitored.

Xanthan polymer is widely used to impart viscosity to water-based drilling fluids³. In addition, several other chemicals are added to improve the drilling fluid characteristics. A lubricant is added to reduce friction between the drill-pipe and bore walls, and a shale stabilizer is added to reduce dispersion and hydration of active claystone formations from the water-based drilling fluids. Besides additives, the drilling fluid picks up certain materials during the drilling operation, such as cutting of the drilled formation, and oil and gas from an active reservoir. The introduction of these additives affects the viscosity of a drilling fluid and thus influences its performance. Another factor affecting the drilling fluid is high temperature from the geothermal gradient in formations and from the heat generated due to friction between the drill bit and borehole wall. The high temperature reduces the fluid viscosity and decreases the effectiveness of a drilling fluid.

The fluid viscosity is measured using different rheometer geometries : concentric-cylinders and cone-and-plate geometry. While a concentric-geometry applies a non-homogenous shear to the fluid sample contained in the annulus, a cone-and-plate geometry imparts a uniform shear across the sample⁴. Therefore, a comparison of the viscosities measured using these two geometries can describe the impact of rheometer geometry on drilling fluid characteristics.

In this study, we have evaluated the effects of rheometer geometry, drilling fluid additives and temperature on the viscosity of xanthan based drilling fluids. One unique aspect of this study is that we have combined several viscosity curves to a single curve using parameters obtained from the molecular theories of polymers. Such normalization of the viscosities of the drilling fluid containing additives has never been tried before.

Results and Discussion

Effect of temperature on drilling fluid viscosity :

The viscosities of the drilling fluids as a function of shear rate at different temperatures are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Fig. 1 illustrates the viscosities of drilling fluid A1, and Fig. 2 the viscosities of fluid B6. These figures display the measured viscosities of few compositions, though measurements were made on all fluid compositions shown in Tables 1 and 2. The viscosity responses of the fluid compositions not shown here were similar to those shown.

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Fig. 1. Effect of temperature on the viscosities of drilling fluid A1

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature on the viscosities of drilling fluid B6

Table 1. Composition of drilling fluid A

Sl. no	Composition	Fluid label
1	Xanthan solution (8.26 kg/m ³)	A1
2	Xanthan solution + 1% by vol lubricant	A2
3	Xanthan solution + 3% by vol lubricant	A3
4	Xanthan solution + 3% lubricant + 0.5% vol rev-dust	A4
5	Xanthan solution + 3% lubricant + 1% vol rev-dust	A5
6	Xanthan solution + 3% lubricant + 2% vol rev-dust	A6

Table 2. Composition of drilling fluid B

Sl. no	Composition	Fluid label
1.	Xanthan solution (6.36 kg/m ³)	B1
2	Xanthan solution + encapsulator (11.4 kg/m ³)	B2
3	Xanthan solution + encapsulator + 1.5% by vol lubricant 1	B3
4	Xanthan solution + encapsulator + 1.5% lubricant 1 + 0.5% by vol lubricant 2	B4
5	Xanthan solution + encapsulator + 1.5% lubricant 1 + 0.5% lubricant 2 + 1.3% vol rev-dust	B5
6.	Xanthan solution + encapsulator + 1.5% lubricant 1 + 0.5% lubricant 2 + 2% vol rev-dust	B6

Figs. 1 and 2 illustrate that the drilling fluids exhibit non-Newtonian behavior with a Newtonian plateau at low shear rate and a shear-thinning Power law region at higher shear rates. As the temperature was increased, the fluid viscosities decreased in both the Newtonian plateau and the pseudoplastic regions of the curves. The decrease in viscosities with temperature was due to thermal-breaking of xanthan polymer chains. This thermal-thinning of the polymer was more significant at higher temperatures, as seen in a larger decrease in the viscosities.

The influence of temperature on viscosities was more prominent in drilling Fluid B than in A. This is possibly because of a lower xanthan polymer concentration in Fluid B, 6.36 as compared to 8.26 kg/m³ in Fluid A. A lower viscosity decrease in the higher concentration fluid means that if similar number of bonds were broken in the xanthan molecule at elevated temperature, the fluid having higher polymer concentration had plenty of unbroken bonds to maintain the resulting fluid viscosities. Thus, higher concentration of xanthan polymer provided a thermal stabilization to the drilling fluid.

The drilling fluids formulated in the present study did not contain any gel stabilizer. So, the thermal stabilization was only obtained from the higher xanthan polymer concentration.

Reduction to master curves : The viscosity values at different temperatures were then reduced to master curves. The molecular theories suggest normalization of viscosity as $\left(\frac{\mu - \mu_s}{\mu_o - \mu_s}\right)$ and that of shear rate as $\left(\gamma \frac{(\mu_o - \mu_s)M}{CRT}\right)$, where M is the molecular weight, C the polymer concentration, R the universal gas constant, T the fluid temperature, μ_s and μ_o are respectively the solvent viscosity and upper Newtonian plateau viscosity of fluid at respective concentration and temperature⁵. The concentrations of the xanthan gum used in the present study were 6.36 and 8.26 kg/m³, which were much higher than the overlap concentration (0.4–2 kg/m³) of the xanthan gum⁶. So, the xanthan solutions were in the semi-dilute concentration regime. Figs. 1 and 2 also depict that the viscosities of the drilling fluids in the Newtonian plateau and the shear-thinning regions were very much greater than the viscosity of the solvent water, therefore, the normalization parameters were simplified to $\left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_o}\right)$ and $\left(\gamma \frac{\mu_o M}{CRT}\right)$.

The molecular weight of the xanthan polymer was approximately 3.5×10^6 kg/kg-mole⁷. Since the additives used in this study were clay stabilizers, lubricants and rev-dust,

these chemicals did not alter the molecular behavior of xanthan but merely changed its flow characteristics. Therefore, the xanthan polymer properties such as molecular weight and concentration would not change in the drilling fluids containing additives. So the xanthan polymer properties were used for normalizing and generating master curves from the viscosity-shear rate data measured in different drilling fluid compositions.

The master curve thus generated for drilling fluid A1 is shown in Fig. 3 and that for B6 in Fig. 4. The master curves show very good normalization of the viscosity-shear rate curves from different temperatures to a single curve. Further, since the curves were well normalized even for the fluid with additives, the additives had negligible influence on the molecular properties of xanthan polymer.

Fig. 3. Master curve for drilling fluid A1.

Fig. 4. Master curve for drilling fluid B6.

The normalization parameters used to draw the curves in Figs. 3 and 4 contained polymer concentration, hence the curves for drilling fluids A1 and B1 can be further combined because these fluids contain only xanthan polymer and no additives. Fig. 5 shows the normalized viscosities of the drilling fluids at the two concentrations. The figure shows the successful use of the molecular theories to describe the viscosity data of the xanthan gum solution as a function of temperature, shear rate and polymer concentration. The master curve of Fig. 5 can be modeled by the following equation,

$$\frac{\mu}{\mu_0} = \left[1 + \left(\gamma \frac{\gamma \mu_0 M}{CRT} \right)^2 \right]^{-n} \quad (1)$$

where λ is the dimensionless time constant and n the dimensionless exponent of the viscosity equation. The constant λ was determined to be 3.3 and n to be 0.38 from Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Master curve for drilling fluids A1 and B1 containing xanthan gum.

Significance of the master curves : The master curve provides several advantages for fluid characterization. The foremost benefit is that it was drawn using dimensionless numbers, so a single correlation can describe fluid viscosity as a function of polymer concentration, shear rate and temperature. Secondly, it is a unique technique by which the viscosity measured over limited shear rate, temperature and polymer concentration range can be used to predict the viscosity values at other conditions without actually making viscosity measurements at those conditions.

Fig. 6. Effect of measuring geometry on viscosities of drilling fluid B1 at 75°F.

To illustrate this point, consider fluid A1 viscosity curve at 175°F in Fig. 1. At this temperature, the viscosity was measured at a maximum shear rate of 800 s⁻¹, the upper limit of the rheometer. This shear rate corresponded to a normalized x-axis value of about 2000 in Fig. 3. The master curve, on the other hand, was drawn to the x-axis value of about 10000. Therefore, at 175°F, the viscosity of the fluid can be extrapolated along the master curve to about 5 times

the measured value or to shear rates of 4000 s^{-1} , much higher than the maximum shear rate 800 s^{-1} obtainable with the rheometer.

Effect of measuring geometry on drilling fluid viscosity :

Fig. 6 compares the viscosity values of drilling fluid B1 measured with the different geometries of Bohlin rheometer and Fann viscometer. It displays an excellent agreement in the fluid viscosities measured using different geometries of these viscometers. The agreement implies negligible effect of the rheological instrument on the xanthan solution viscosity. The only difference between the instruments was the range of the shear rates where measurements could be made. The Bohlin rheometer described a wider viscosity curve that included the Newtonian plateau as well as the shear-thinning regions, whereas the Fann viscometer provided the viscosity values in the shear-thinning region only.

Effect of additives on drilling fluid viscosity :

Fig. 7 illustrates the effect of various additives on the

viscosities of drilling fluid A at two temperatures 75 and 200°F. Fig. 8 displays the same effect on the viscosity values of drilling fluid B at the same two temperatures. Figs. 7 and 8 depict a small increase in the viscosity values as different additives were added to the xanthan solution. The increase in the viscosities with additives was more evident at the elevated temperature than at 75°F. Furthermore, the increase in viscosity was mostly obtained from the addition of rev-dust particles.

These figures demonstrate that the various additives would have little influence on the viscosities of the drilling fluid, and that they would not alter the fluid characteristics to suspend and carry drilled-cuttings during a drilling operation. The additives were observed to have beneficial effects on the flow behavior of these fluids⁸. The drilling fluids containing lubricant and encapsulator were observed to exhibit reduced friction pressure losses through tubing and enhanced drag reduction over that obtained with xanthan polymer alone. Moreover, small viscosity increase due to lubricants and rev-dust particles observed in Figs. 7 and 8

(a) Viscosities at 75°F

(b) Viscosities at 200°F

Fig. 7. Effect of additives on the viscosities of drilling fluid A compositions.

(a) Viscosities at 75°F

(b) Viscosities at 200°F

Fig. 8. Effect of additives on the viscosities of drilling fluid B compositions

corresponded to the small increase in pressure drop through the tubing⁸.

Summary :

(i) The xanthan based drilling fluids exhibited non-Newtonian behavior having a Newtonian plateau viscosity at lower shear rates and a shear-thinning region at higher shear rates. The fluid viscosities decreased as the fluid temperature was increased. A higher polymer concentration was observed to thermally stabilize the drilling fluid. (ii) The viscosity-shear rate curves at various temperatures for each fluid were reduced to master curves using parameters defined with molecular theories. The master curves can be used to obtain viscosity values within and beyond the shear rate and temperature limitations of the rheometer. (iii) The effect of measuring geometry was observed to be minimal on the viscosities of xanthan solutions. (iv) There was a slight increase in the viscosities of the drilling fluids due to the presence of additives.

Experimental

The viscosity measurements were made with two concentrations of the xanthan solution. At each concentration, several chemicals were added to the base xanthan solution to simulate real drilling fluids. These chemicals included lubricant, encapsulator (shale stabilizer), and rev-dust. The rev-dust (Milwhite, Inc. Houston, TX, USA) was a calcium montmorillonite clay, used to simulate drilled solids¹. A wet screen analysis of the rev-dust showed 2–5% retained on 200 mesh and 7–10% retained on 325 mesh.

The concentrations and the additives used in the two xanthan solutions, designated fluid A and B, are summarized in Tables 1 and 2. The samples were prepared in the city water by first formulating a xanthan solution, and subsequently adding other chemicals in six stages in the order shown in Tables 1 and 2. At each stage, a fluid sample was withdrawn from the prepared fluid formulation to measure the drilling fluid viscosities using Bohlin CS 50 rheometer and Fann 35 viscometer. Table 3 summarizes the type and dimensions of the geometries used for the viscosity measurements.

The Fann viscometer was used to measure the fluid viscosities at six shear rates from 5 to 1021 s⁻¹ at ambient temperature conditions. The high-pressure cell of the Bohlin rheometer was used to measure the fluid viscosities at

rates from 0.01 to 800 s⁻¹ and temperatures from 75 to 250°F. The cone-and-plate fixture of the Bohlin rheometer was used to measure the fluid viscosities at ambient temperature only.

Table 3. Measuring geometry of the laboratory rheometers

Instrument	Geometry	Dimensions
Fann 35 viscometer	Concentric-cylinders (Inner-cylinder : bob Outer-cylinder : cup)	Diameter of the bob 34.49 mm; Inner diameter of rotor cup 36.83 mm; Ratio of the bob to cup radius 0.936
Bohlin CS 50-rheometer (High pressure cell)	Concentric-cylinders (bob and cup)	Diameter of the rotor bob 25 mm; Inner diameter of the cup 27 mm; Ratio of the bob to cup radius 0.926
Bohlin CS 50 rheometer	Cone and plate	Cone angle 4° and Cone diameter 40 mm

The elevated temperature tests were performed using the hot oil-bath available with the Bohlin rheometer. The measurements at each temperature were made by first raising the sample temperature to the test conditions and allowing the sample to thermally equilibrate for 3 min, and then measuring the sample viscosity. The test parameters were maintained similar in all fluid samples analyzed.

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